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TECHNOLOGICAL ENGLISH TEACHING: VIEWS FROM A FEW PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract: The purpose of this study, "Technological English Teaching: Views From A Few Perspectives" is to investigate the possibility of identifying variables that are pertinent to the instruction of the language using Android applications and video games. Adopting a dogmatic approach to language acquisition is crucial. To achieve the intended goals, innovations are used. Although teaching English to speakers of other languages is a difficult undertaking, the kinks in the system may be worked out by using appropriate techniques. Learning English using video games and Android applications piques students' attention and helps them improve their language proficiency in a fun way. This essay identifies the numerous difficulties encountered when teaching languages and offers workable solutions to resolve the issues. It enumerates the benefits of using Android applications and video games to teach English.

Keywords: Technology; Video game; Android applications; Second language learners.

Introduction

One of the most useful teaching resources for instructors of second languages is educational technology. It includes computers, media, networking devices, smartphones, and tablets. Our daily tasks are now quicker and easier thanks to these modern gadgets. Teenagers love playing video games, which introduce them to a whole new social and cultural environment. It's challenging to teach English as a second language to a diverse collection of pupils in a set amount of time. Therefore, in order to increase student attention, he or she must try various different approaches.

Scholars¹ concur that playing video games helps kids improve their language abilities, but is this practical in a classroom setting? Indeed, there are plenty of opportunities to use video games to learn English. Applications for Android have simplified the procedure. The Play Store offers a variety of apps that encourage students to actively participate in improvisation. Students are greatly impacted by online videos, and they watch videos more intently than they do traditional educational approaches.

In his study "The Educational benefits of video games," Dr. Mark Griffiths, a professor of gambling studies, reports that four volunteers, ages 11 to 17, who had been diagnosed with impulse control issues, played video games for four weeks. Following the experimental trial, the subjects showed increased cooperation and enthusiasm for the treatment.

Benefits of using video games to teach languages

Playing games in class encourages participation from the students in group projects. They will benefit from studying more while having fun when learning English is integrated into the games they play. In comparison to traditional teaching methods, this means that more learning topics are covered in the same amount of time. The following are some benefits of utilizing video games in language instruction:

- ✓ It is widely accessible.
- ✓ It supports kids' goal-setting, record-keeping, and behavioral modifications.
- ✓ It is entertaining, which piques participants' intense attention.

Playing video games provides a way to learn and discover how to accomplish things, allowing one to "learn by doing." The teacher's role is limited to supervising the students and providing assistance during challenging circumstances. Playing games improves listening comprehension as the player must pay attention to the English instructions, directives, and advice that are provided. The player is able to advance to the next level or be promoted for continued play thanks to these guidelines and advice. The directions and directives that the pupils have heard are to be written down. Additionally, they are required to write down any unfamiliar or challenging terms they encounter. Thus, the pupils make an effort to retain certain phrases and terms.

High definition cable hook-ups are accepted by the sources that may be used to play video games, including the Microsoft Xbox 360, Sony Play Station 3, and projectors and displays. Additionally, PC gaming is more affordable and useful than Play Station gaming.

Teachers' role in using technology

Teachers nowadays must be conscious of the new tasks and obligations that the newest technology has placed upon them. It is expected of the students to think critically, solve problems, collaborate with others in a team, and act. The role of the teacher in the modern society must go beyond imparting information. The creation and use of new technologies in the classroom will determine how the role of the teacher changes. It is necessary to alter the classroom setting. This gives the job of the teacher and facilitator², who facilitates advancement, a new meaning.

Several video games from the viewpoint of pupils

For kids from regional backgrounds, acquiring a language may be an arduous and even unpleasant job. To comprehend, generate, and use the target language, one must constantly exert effort. Among the video games that aid in English language acquisition for pupils are

¹ Scholars- A **scholar** is a person who is a researcher or has expertise in an academic discipline.

² Facilitator- someone who helps a person or organization do something more easily

The era of empires

Initiative IGI

A Farmhouse

The Empire Era

The multiplayer feature of the warrior game Age of Empires helps pupils interact with one another. The game aids in the learners' comprehension of the instructions by having them trade raw resources, buy and sell things, and ultimately wage war against the enemy islands. It improves their reading and listening comprehension.

Project IGI

The army game Project IGI is networked to the server so that it may be played by everybody at a specific time. In order to assault the terrorists, players must obey the head commando's directions in this game. They learn new terminology and improve their listening abilities as a result.

Agricultural Home

Players may exchange meat, eggs, vegetables, and fruits from villages to cities by playing the game Farm House. Students may learn the names of fruits, plants, and animals—words that aren't typically used in daily life—by playing this game. Through these firsthand encounters, students learn how to translate abstract concepts into concrete ones that may come in handy in their everyday lives. Players from all around the world are connected via these online games. Students engage in a variety of language-related activities at school, including group projects, reading, writing, discussing, and arguing. There are instances when pupils continue to be passive learners and show little interest in them. One way to characterize gaming is as a collection of useful social behaviors.

Educating Using Apps: The mobile app market is evolving quickly. The use of Android smartphones is prevalent. Students in Rajasthan have been given Android tablets by the government. It is an excellent tool for second language instructors. Apple's well-known tagline, "There's an App for that," richly suggests that everything is possible. The Play Store offers millions of Android applications³. There are many options for teachers and students to utilize the programs according to their preferences and interests. These apps are useful technological resources that teachers may utilize to help students learn English.

A few applications for teaching English:

The dictionary definition of android is "a human who resembles automation." The actual meaning of its name is that it refers to the software stack developed by Google for the purpose of developing extensive mobile applications and software that allow users to fully utilize the capabilities of their mobile devices. Through features like

- ✓ The tenses of English;
- ✓ Synonyms and Antonyms;
- ✓ Word games [to increase vocabulary]
- ✓ Spelling checker

³ Android applications- Android apps are software applications that run on mobile devices powered by the Android operating system.

- ✓ Sentence builder
- ✓ Phonetics

Conclusion:

This essay seeks to inspire students by using plausible and useful theories, as well as the utilization of Android applications and video games in the classroom. Anything that is novel is guaranteed to grab students' interest. Most researchers concur that using innovations will increase the effectiveness of language teaching and learning. Our world is dominated by Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp. The globe has gotten smaller as a result of communication technology improvements. While using technology to teach English lightens the workload for teachers, it also sparks a great deal of interest in both teachers and students as it keeps students engaged throughout the lesson.

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